

Minutes of the 60th Experimenters' Meeting The Cosener's House, Abingdon, 1st February 2018

(This document was finalised on 13th July 2018)

Present:

(BJB)	Dr Barbara Brooks ^{1,7}	
(CJW)	Dr Chris Walden ^{3,5}	
(DAH)	Dr David Hooper ^{4,5}	Secretary
(DK)	Dr Dirk Klugmann ⁵	
(GAP)	Dr Graham Parton ^{2,5}	
(GV)	Prof Geraint Vaughan ⁶	Chair
(HMAR)	Dr Hugo Ricketts ⁶	
(LD)	Mr Les Dean ⁴	

Affiliation:

- ¹Atmospheric Measurement Facility (AMF)
- ²Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA)
- ³Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric Radar Research (CFARR)
- ⁴NERC MST Radar Facility
- ⁵STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)
- ⁶University of Manchester
- ⁷University of Leeds

Other abbreviations used in this document:

BLWP	Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPW	Dave Wareing (University of Manchester technician)
EUCOS	EUMETNET Composite Observing System
MST(R)(F)	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NCAS	National Centre for Atmospheric Science
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council
UPS	Uninterruptable Power Supply
UTC	(Coordinated) Universal Time
v3/v4	MST Radar processing versions 3/4

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

GAP reported that the web link on page 3 for providing statistics of MSTRF dataset usage did not work.

DAH checked this out after the meeting and found that line-wrapping caused the address to be split into two on GAP's computer. Curiously, the link worked when DAH tried it on two other computers. The word "year" had been omitted, in the 2nd paragraph of section 3d, where DAH was trying to refer to the septic tank's 25 year lifetime. The minutes of the 59th meeting were otherwise accepted as correct.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

Item 47.2.1 has received no action since DAH has been concentrated on the following two action items.

ACTION ITEM 47.2.2 DAH to ensure, as soon as possible, that MST radar data products generated by the latest version of the signal processing software are available for the entire observation archive.

SUPERSEDED

ACTION ITEM 59.4.1 DAH to create v4 Cardinal files for all dates back to mid 2011 as soon as possible.

COMPLETED

DAH reported that he had created version 4.0 Cardinal files for the period from 1st June 2011 to the present. This means that item 59.4.1, which superseded 47.2.2, has been completed. GV requested that the back processing be extended to the earliest date for which v3 Cartesian files are available. DAH will need to complete action item 47.2.1. before the back processing can be extended even further.

ACTION ITEM 60.2.1 DAH to extend the availability of the v4 Cardinal files back to the earliest date for which v3 Cartesian files are available.

NEW

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had not had time to make any progress with item 47.3.2. Nevertheless, his software for handling raw LD40 data files is almost ready for use. In response to GV's query, DAH clarified that the data from the Vaisala WXT520 were also not currently being made available for the same reason. GV emphasised the usefulness of the latter dataset owing to the fact that it was the only one to provide pressure measurements.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.1 DAH to increase the storage capacity of the Frongoch data logger so that communications failures do not lead to data loss.

ONGOING

DAH reported that Judith Jeffery, from the Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric Radar Research (CFARR), had started to assess the stabilities of different Campbell Scientific data loggers, since a new one is also needed for one of their sites. Recent problems with the existing Frongoch data logger - see section 4b - have made this action item more urgent.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.2 DAH to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar permanently available to users if the Met Office will allow this.

ONGOING

DAH has made no progress on the above action item. GV pointed out that the Met Office's statistics had proved to be a useful way of demonstrating the MST radar's data quality for the recent NERC funding renewal application. Consequently DAH should ensure that the statistics continue to be accessible. GAP suggested that it might be possible for them to be delivered to the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA) through the existing mechanism for acquiring files from the Met Office.

ACTION ITEM 58.1.1 DAH to consult with members of the data user community in order to establish the sort of instrument performance details that would be useful.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he has been in contact with Chris Lee, who was probably the only person for whom this action item was important.

ACTION ITEM 58.1.2 GAP to assign a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to the NERC MSTRF's Vaisala WXT510 dataset.

COMPLETED

GAP reported that this had been completed and that the DOI - <http://dx.doi.org/10.5285/63c30b6310faa22e90b7e4a7adce1fa2> - directed to the CEDA catalogue page for the WXT510.

ACTION ITEM 59.3.1 DAH to arrange for the clearance of willow saplings from the MST radar's antenna array as soon as possible.

NEW

DAH reported that he had made some progress on this. Someone in the RAL Estates team has given him details of a company that RAL use for "Facilities Management" work. GV reported that Dave Wareing (DPW) was concerned about trees that are overhanging the lidar installation. Ideally these could be cut back at the same time. However, they are growing just outside of the perimeter fence and so it will be necessary to first find out who owns the land.

3. Facility Report - DAH

Full details of facility and instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3a) Data Management

GAP began this section by reporting on recent developments at CEDA. The data catalogue is now able to include links between related datasets. For example, the dataset page for each version of MST Radar data products has links to all other versions - see e.g. the "*Related Datasets*" tab on the version 3 page, <http://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/6d9a74e917d04cde9f0f7fa5fb3a9dd4>. GAP will soon extend this facility (where applicable) to cover the other datasets within the MSTRF's collection.

The number of people accessing the MSTRF's datasets during the past 6 months has dropped relative to the previous reporting period. Moreover, most of the recent users have only been interested in quick-look plots. GAP added that it is common to see large variations in the number of people accessing datasets following the natural cycle of the academic year. GV wondered whether 6 months is maybe too short a period for tracking significant changes. GAP noted that usage of the new version 4 MST radar

data files was starting to increase.

BJB gave a short report on the National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS) data project. Data from all Atmospheric Measurement Facility (AMF) instruments will adopt the new NCAS data standards by 1st April 2018. These standards add an extra NCAS-specific layer on top of the existing Climate and Forecasts (CF) metadata standards. The next step will be to extend the scope of the project to include instruments operated by the the MSTRF and CFARR. These facilities will merge with the AMF in 2020.

DAH reported that he had contributed a python-based tool for creating metadata templates to the NCAS data project. This separates the descriptive task of defining/composing the metadata from the technical tasks of processing the data and writing them to a file. This makes it very easy to modify the metadata - even by adding or removing entire fields - without having to make changes to the processing software. DAH's software is openly-accessible under a GNU General Public License (GPL) - <https://github.com/ncasuk/metadata-from-template>.

3b) Electricity - DAH

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units experienced 11 short-lived (i.e. no more than 1 s) input power problems during the past 6 months. Four of these occurred between 25th and 31st December 2017.

The most significant electricity supply problem occurred during the early morning of 20th October 2017. This happened to be the first day of DAH being away on two weeks' leave and being uncontactable. There were 10 instances of problems lasting approximately 5 s each before the UPS units became fully discharged at around 02:45 UTC. LD spotted the problem and visited the site in order to restart the MST radar at 10:33 UTC. Unfortunately, the beam steering unit failed to steer the beam away from the vertical (probably as a result of equipment not being powered up in the right order), leading to unrealistic horizontal wind profiles. After being unable to find anyone to give him help, LD stopped and then restarted the radar at 16:53 UTC, which led to the problem being cleared.

3c) Telecommunications

There have been no problems during the past 6 months.

3d) Miscellaneous

It appears that the green shed suffered from flooding on 21st January 2018, when there was prolonged and heavy rainfall in the area. LD thinks that the flooding was the result of the nearby brook becoming blocked by debris collecting under a small bridge. GV commented that he had been in Aberystwyth at the time and that the amount of rain had been exceptional. He added that this event highlighted the need to not store items on the floor of the shed.

GV gave a short update on NERC's National Capability (NC) commissioning exercise. The MSTRF has applied for only 25% of its funding through the existing "facility" route. This is intended to support individual users and/or projects. The other 75% has been applied for as part of NCAS's bid for "underpinning" activities, i.e long term measurements that benefit all users. Reviewers' comments regarding the underpinning bid have been very positive. GV is still waiting for feedback on the facility bid.

CJW drew attention to the fact that the text for the NERC Service Level Agreement (SLA) would need to be modified to reflect this new arrangement. GV advised that such text should be flexible, e.g. so that new instruments could be operated at the site without the need for changes to be made. He pointed out that NERC was starting to think about funding for its Hazardous Weather theme and that there is likely to be money available for new equipment. However, the funding will not cover the staff time required to keep the equipment in operation.

DAH drew attention to an article about the chemtrail conspiracy theory that had appeared on the BBC's website on the day before the meeting - <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/blogs-trending-42195511>. Unlike some articles that DAH has seen on this topic, the BBC one is clear in regarding the belief in chemtrails as completely nonsensical. The article refers to a recent peer-reviewed article entitled "Quantifying expert consensus against the existence of a secret, large-scale atmospheric spraying program" - <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-9326/11/8/084011/pdf>. DAH recommended referring to both of these articles for anyone having to respond to enquiries on the topic.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

There were a number of days between late June (27th, 28th, and 29th) and late July (3rd, 18th, and 19th) 2017 when the tipping bucket raingauge detected no rain despite the fact that the Vaisala WXT520 had done so. The daily accumulations reported by the WXT520 ranged from 0.1 to 2.5 mm. However, since the tipping bucket detected rain on 20th July without any intervention having been taken, it is possible that the rain fell slowly enough for it to evaporate before it had accumulated the 0.2 mm necessary to cause a tip. It is already known that daily accumulations measured by the two instruments can differ widely - see section 6d of the minutes for the 58th meeting.

The tipping bucket raingauge detected no rain on 21st September 2017, despite the fact that the WXT520 detected 5.0 mm. When LD inspected it on the following day, he found that its filter gauze had become blocked. Despite the fact that he cleaned it, the instrument failed to detect any rain later the same day (i.e. on the 22nd) or on the 24th or 27th September. Although the accumulation detected by the WXT520 was no more than 0.5 mm on the first two occasions, it was 7.9 mm for the 27th September. In order to check whether or not the raingauge was working, LD poured large quantities of water into it during the periods 09:00 - 09:10 and 10:50 - 11:00 UTC on 29th September. These were detected and DAH blanked the data before the corresponding NASA Ames file was created. DAH's file creation software has been specifically designed to allow this sort of blanking.

DAH is in the process of creating a public engagement resource based on a visualisation of data from the pyranometer, which measures the solar radiation flux density. The Campbell Scientific data logger uses these measurements to infer whether or not each 10 minute interval counts as a sunshine period. DAH was inspired to look at the data whilst creating a visualisation of daily cloud cover, based on Vaisala LD40 observations, for artist Mat Chivers - see section 3d of the minutes for the 58th meeting. However, rather than presenting the daily number of sunshine hours along a separate horizontal time line for each year, he wrapped them around a spiral. The Head of Communications for the RAL Space department liked this "*Sunshine Spiral*" so much that she used it on a commemorative gift for Dame Julia Slingo when she attended the Appleton Conference in December 2017. A photograph of Dame Julia accepting this gift can be seen on the following page - <https://www.ralspace.stfc.ac.uk/Pages/13th-Appleton-Space-Conference.aspx>. DAH is currently creating further material to explain what the sunshine spiral is showing. He hopes to make the resource publicly available within the next few months.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

There have been problems with the data logger since late on the 8th November 2017. Initially only the direction measurements were affected, staying unrealistically close to northerly for almost two weeks. Since the wind direction at the lowest MST radar range gates was predominantly northerly for the first half of this period, DAH did not initially realise that there was a problem. LD removed the connecting cable for the wind vane on 21st November and brought it back to Capel Dewi for tests (after this, the direction readings stayed close to southerly). Although the cable looked weathered (it has been in use for at least 15 years), it still appeared to be robust from an electrical point of view. Nevertheless, DAH ordered replacement cables for both the wind vane and anemometer as well as a new wind vane. LD

wasn't able to install the new components until 16th January 2018, owing to a lack of suitable weather and the availability of someone to help him winch down the wind tower. Frustratingly, both the wind speed and wind direction readings cut out between approximately 18:00 and 22:00 UTC of the following day (17th January), just as Storm Fionn passed over - see section 6a. LD suspected that the wind tower might have been struck by lightning. He visited Frongoch on 19th January and inspected the logger, power-cycling it for good measure. DAH re-uploaded the acquisition software later the same afternoon. However, none of this solved the problem. Since then the availability of useful data has been intermittent. DAH showed the plot for 29th January 2018, which showed high-frequency oscillations in both wind speed and direction. He had never seen such a pattern before and wondered whether it was real or the result of a logger problem. GV pointed out that satellite images for this date showed interesting cloud patterns, suggesting that the oscillations were real.

In the context of replacing the data logger at Frongoch, i.e. action item 51.4.1, DAH pointed out that the newer Campbell Scientific models allow connections to be made via 3G mobile phone links. The existing logger relies on an Aberystwyth University land line, over which the MSTRF has no control. BJB recommended using a modem with a directional antenna if reception at Frongoch is a problem. She has used such a modem for her data logger on top of Ben Nevis. She also suggested that a sonic anemometer could be attached to the tower in addition to the existing wind vane and anemometer. This would provide redundancy. GV emphasised the importance of the surface wind measurements for studying extreme weather events.

4c) Vaisala WXT520 surface met and wind sensors

Formatted data from this instrument are not yet available owing to DAH having had a lack of time. There is a gap in the raw data between 20th October and 6th November 2017. This was the result of the acquisition software not restarting automatically after a power cut - see section 3b.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

Formatted data from this instrument are not yet available owing to DAH having had a lack of time. Nevertheless, he showed the latest 24 hour plot for 15/16 October 2017 at the time of Storm Ophelia. The small region of backscatter seen between 07:30 and 09:30 UTC on the 16th had reminded him of the possible signature of volcanic ash. The backscatter power was intermediate between the typical values for the boundary layer (low) and clouds (high). He had immediately reported this to GV and HMAR, who were already operating their own lidars at the radar site - see section 6b.

4e) Sky Cameras

During July and August 2017, DAH published 6 time-lapse videos from images taken by the original sky camera. These are available through the CEDA document repository under a Creative Commons Attribution license, which means that anyone may access and make use of them. Their web addresses are of the form <http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1298/>, with the final 4 digits being unique to each one:

- 1298 Cirrostratus clouds giving rise to a 22° halo around the Sun
- 1301 development of Cumulus congestus clouds, leading to a rain shower and a rainbow
- 1308 Altocumulus clouds displaying both undulatus and lenticularis features
- 1309 Altocumulus lenticularis clouds revealing Mountain Wave activity
- 1310 widespread development of Cumulonimbus clouds, some of which have extensive Anvils
- 1311 Cumulonimbus cloud development at sunset

As a result of analysing some of the images from Sky-Camera-2 in connection with his vacation student project - see section 6c - DAH noticed that the camera's elevation angle had dipped slightly since it was installed in late 2014. This was corrected on 19th January 2018, with the elevation angle being set slightly higher than originally in case it droops again.

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

DAH showed an image taken by the NLC camera on the morning of 28th July 2017, which showed NLCs. He also showed the image taken at 02:30:01 UTC on 19th July. This had fortuitously captured the bulbous base of a cumulonimbus cloud illuminated by a lightning discharge.

DAH pointed out that images from the NLC camera and from Sky-Camera-2 have not yet been delivered to the CEDA archive. He is waiting until he has decided on how best to use the available metadata fields to be consistent with NCAS's data standards. BJB recommended that DAH should implement the metadata as he sees best. The NCAS data project can then follow his lead. The priority should be on getting the files into the archive.

4g) MST Radar

DAH began by presenting model-comparison statistics for the past six months, which had been prepared by Caroline Bulpett of the Met Office. He began with those from EUCOS. Data availability has been fairly constant, although there were a couple of days with very low values in late December 2017. The reason for these is not clear. The root mean square wind mean vector differences were mostly below the 5.0 m s^{-1} target maximum. Much larger values on 20th October 2017 correspond to the beam steering unit problems following a power cut - see section 3b. Comparisons against the Met Office's UKV model also show good data quality over the past six months.

DAH then gave a general instrument performance report. The transmitters have been relatively reliable over the past six months. TXB blew its fuse on only two occasions. There have been numerous instances of TXE's output power being slightly lower than expected for the duration of a single dwell. However, it has remained in operation. There have been a few occasions when the radar has suffered from interference, although this has primarily resulted in reduced altitude coverage rather than in contaminated winds. The problem was particularly noticeable on 27th January 2018.

The radar was stopped during the morning and then again during the afternoon of 18th July 2017. This was to allow LD to put a dummy load in place of one of the power splitters that was allowing radio frequency signals through but not the direct current ones. The power splitters are bespoke items and there are no spares that can be used to replace the problem one. Although LD thinks that he can fix it electrically, it would need to be thoroughly resealed for use back in the field. CJW recommended speaking to Chilbolton Observatory staff about possible ways forward.

During August and September 2017, LD conducted a programme of testing the spare beam steering units in order to establish which ones are in working order. This involved him installing them for a week each (in position 100, which is closest to the site bungalow) and then monitoring the readings. It turns out that the company that supplied the beam steering units still have 6 spare units in stock. LD thought that it would be a good idea to invest in these.

DAH has withheld from the CEDA archives the version 3 (v3) Cartesian files for a number of days that show unrealistic winds: 15th October 2017; 26th, 28th, and 29th November 2017; 8th and 15th December 2017; 28th January 2018. In all of these cases, the unrealistic winds were confined to narrow time and altitude ranges. DAH will need to develop a tool for changing the reliability flags within such regions before he can release the files to the archive. These gaps prohibit the creation of version 4 Cardinal files for one day to either side of the date with a missing v3 file. This is because the v4 processing smooths the horizontal wind data with a running mean and expects to find the v3 files within the archive. It will be relatively easy to modify the v4 processing software so that it additionally searches the directory where rejected v3 files are kept. DAH has reprocessed the entire observation archive back to June 2011.

LD reported that he had seen a localised increase in radar return power from the mesosphere at the time of an intense solar flare - at 12:02 UTC on 6th September 2017. DAH had subsequently spotted a similar

case by looking back through the archive.

5. Guest Instrument Report

DAH reported that Ben Pickering, a PhD student at the University of Leeds, has been operating a laser disdrometer at the radar site since early 2017. The instrument measures the size and fall speed of hydrometeors, which allows it to determine whether they are liquid water, ice, or mixed phase. Ben is happy to make the data available to anyone who might be interested. He has produced a short video of his round-Britain journey to deploy instruments at a number of sites: https://youtu.be/SZLJq_mT288.

GV reported that the Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler (BLWP) is currently in operation at Capel Dewi. It will remain there for some time since it is not currently required for any field campaigns. The primary aim is continue the work begun by Chris Lee looking at systematic differences between vertical velocities measured by the BLWP and by the MST radar. Consequently it is important that the instrument is aligned extremely carefully so that the vertical beam can be guaranteed to be pointing as close to vertical as is possible.

The BLWP has suffered from several software problems since it returned from Portugal. For example, DPW was unable to get it started for a whole week before it came to life by itself. Moreover, there have been problems with the function for automatically changing the width of Doppler spectra in response to changes in the maximum observed wind speed. This resulted in velocity-aliasing during the recent Storm Fionn - see section 6a. DK commented that when he had been in charge of the Met Office's BLWPs, he had disabled the function for the same reason.

HMAR reported that the Elight lidar is working well and can now be operated in photon counting mode. DPW is ready to start upgrading the Raman lidar. The UV lidar attracts insects, whose remains are subsequently splattered over the optics leading to reduced signals. After cleaning, the return signals have been so much stronger that it has been necessary to make use of attenuators in order to prevent the photomultiplier from saturating. HMAR would like to add water vapour detection capability. His priority is to get the Elight and Raman lidars working together. GV is writing up his analysis of the detection of smoke during May 2016 for Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics. HMAR will write something up on observations made during Storm Ophelia - see section 6c.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) Storm Fionn - GV

GV presented an analysis of the observational data associated with the passage of storm Fionn, which was rather different to typical winter storms. The pressure charts for 17th and 18th January 2018 show a very small scale low pressure system developing via a non-Shapiro-Kaiser mechanism. There were strong winds between the fronts, just behind the cold front, and to the southern side of the low. The maximum recorded gust speed in the British Isles was 93 mph at Capel Curig in north Wales. However, the most significant impacts - in terms of trees being toppled, structural damage, and loss of electricity - were in the eastern counties of England. The storm caused transport chaos in Holland and Germany, where it was known as storm Friederike.

The 300 hPa charts show a strong and very straight jet stream across the Atlantic. The 850 hPa charts show a perturbation in the boundary between the warm and cold air sectors. The temperature measurements at Capel Dewi clearly indicate the passages of the associated warm and cold fronts, with changes of around 4°C approximately 5 hours apart (a number of other sudden warm air sectors have been seen this winter). Unfortunately there is a gap in the Frongoch wind sensor measurements between approximately 18:00 and 21:45 UTC on the 17th - see section 4b for more details - when the surface wind speed

appears to have peaked.

Throughout the passage of the system, the BLWP showed wind speeds of at least 20 m/s down to the lowest observable levels (200 m above ground level). There was a tongue of faster moving air associated with the warm front, with speeds of up to 40 m/s at altitudes above 1000 m. There is a similar feature associated with the cold front. The observations made using the high mode suffered from velocity aliasing (see section 5) and there were many regions where the data were tagged as being unreliable. The low mode data were more robust. The MST radar (version 4) data show 3 narrow regions of enhanced wind speeds (above 40 m/s), one of which is associated with the warm front. There is a well-defined wind shear associated with the cold front, which does not have a classic form.

The Met Office's surface stations show that the strongest gust winds occurred after 00:00 UTC on the 18th. However, the associated mean wind speeds were not that high. The temperature data clearly reveal the passage of the warm sector. Data from the University of Manchester's Whitworth Observatory show mean wind speeds of up to 17.5 m/s within the warm air sector and gust speeds of up to 27 m/s. GV reported that he probably won't have time to take this analysis much further. Nevertheless, he would be interested to see the surface wind data from the WXT520 instrument at Capel Dewi. BJB reported that she operates an automatic weather station in the Dee Estuary and that the temperature data for this period also showed the large changes at the fronts.

6b) Red sun: dust or smoke? - HMAR

HMAR presented an analysis of the atmospheric conditions encountered on 16th October 2017, when red skies were seen across large parts of the British Isles. The NCAS (Elight) ozone/aerosol profiler was operated at Capel Dewi whilst a SigmaSpace/EnviroTech MiniMPL (micro pulse lidar) was operated at Brighton. The "RGB" composite satellite image for 12:00 UTC on the 16th shows the spiral of clouds associated with Storm Ophelia, which was to the west of mainland Britain. It also shows a band of cloud and dust stretching from the western Iberian peninsular up to the British Isles. The shadow of the dust can be seen on the sea in the satellite image for the previous evening.

There are two potential sources for this dust. The satellite image for the 13th October shows dust being blown off the Sahara. The images for 15th October show pyrocumulus clouds, which formed as a result of forest fires in Portugal. The ECMWF forecast plots for aerosols from biomass burning show a weak layer to the east of the British Isles. The aerosol layer seen by the Elight lidar was so thick that at times the laser light could not penetrate the entire depth. In order to distinguish between backscatter from smoke and from dust, HMAR has considered the lidar ratio, i.e. between the extinction and backscatter coefficients. The large values suggest that smoke particles predominate. The backscatter seen by the Vaisala LD40 ceilometer also shows up the base of the smoke layer. However, because the laser light was absorbed by it, the full depth was not revealed. DPW had operated the sun photometer, which measures the aerosol optical depth at several wavelengths. However, it was very difficult to align the instrument with the Sun owing to how obscured it was by the smoke layer.

Data from the miniMPL instrument at Brighton show similar patterns, with a thick diffuse layer passing over. Since the layer was moving more slowly at this location, the red sky effect lasted for longer. The values of depolarisation ratio close to 0.0 indicate that the scattering particles are close to spherical. HMAR also looked at lidar observations made at the University of Hertfordshire's Bayfordbury campus. The time of arrival and duration of the layer were different at each of the 3 sites. The layer was also seen by the 35 GHz cloud radar at Chilbolton. CJW pointed out that, unfortunately, the 94 GHz was not in operation at the time and so it was not possible to estimate the size of the backscattering particles by comparing the observations made at the two frequencies. Although the International Space Station flew over southern Britain during the afternoon, the signature of the cloud as observed by its (lidar) Cloud-Aerosol Transit System (CATS) appears to be surprisingly insignificant. Nevertheless, HMAR has downloaded the data and will investigate this in more detail. He finished by showing NASA God-

ard's time-lapse video of the hurricanes and aerosols simulation for the autumn 2017 season - available from <https://svs.gsfc.nasa.gov/12772>. This clearly shows dust and smoke being drawn northwards by the approach of Storm Ophelia. BJB wondered if the raw data from Ben Pickering's laser disdrometer were available and whether or not the particles would give rise to a distinct signature.

6c) The signature of clouds observed by the MST Radar - DAH

DAH presented highlights from work carried out by Kieran Pope, who had undertaken a Vacation Student placement with him at RAL during the summer of 2017. The project was motivated by the fact that there are often distinctive features in MST radar (vertical beam) signal power and (beam-broadening) corrected (vertical beam) spectral width associated with clouds. The signal power is expected to be determined by the square of the mean vertical gradient of potential refractive index, M^2 , which depends on the specific humidity, its vertical gradient, and the static stability (i.e. the vertical gradient of potential temperature). The corrected spectral width gives a measure of turbulence intensity. Enhanced (range-squared corrected) backscatter power observed by the Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer indicates the location of hydrometeors. However, the laser light often cannot penetrate much above the cloud base, which leads to a limited observable altitude range. No details are available of the algorithm used by the manufacturer to derive cloud base altitudes.

DAH began with an example of the approach of a low pressure system on 24th November 2012. The LD40 backscatter power shows the cloud base descending from the high to the low troposphere over the course of the morning. Throughout a prolonged period of rain during the afternoon, a reduction in the backscatter power can be seen within a narrow layer at an altitude slightly above 1 km above mean sea level. DAH suspected that this corresponded to a melting layer and so referred to it as a "dark band", in reference to the corresponding "bright band" seen by radars (GV agreed with this interpretation). During the morning, the region immediately beneath the cloud base is characterised by enhanced values of MST radar signal power and enhanced values of corrected spectral width. The signal power enhancement is consistent with an increase in M^2 as a result of the large (positive) humidity gradient seen in radiosonde data (DAH has not yet carried out a quantitative comparison). Moreover, the spectral width enhancement is consistent with turbulence generation through convective instability as a result of evaporative cooling as hydrometeors fall into the dry layer beneath the cloud.

The base of stratocumulus clouds is typically below the lowest observable MST radar range gate (1.6 km above mean sea level). Nevertheless, the presence of such clouds can be revealed by persistently enhanced values of corrected spectral width at the lowest range gates. Turbulence generation is expected as a result of convective instabilities within the clouds. For the example observed on 20th September 2012, the MST radar signal power was enhanced immediately above the region of enhanced corrected spectral widths. The signal power enhancement is consistent with an increase in M^2 as a result of the large (negative) humidity gradient and increase in static stability (seen in radiosonde data) that cap stratocumulus clouds. Altocumulus clouds are also sometimes found to be capped by such conditions, e.g. on 21st July 2011. However, the turbulence associated with altocumulus can sometimes be seen below the cloud base, sometimes above it, and sometimes (as in this case) spread to either side.

7. Any Other Business

GV recommended that DAH should prioritise replacing the Frongoch data logger and making WXT520 and LD40 data available through CEDA. BJB thought it would be useful to have a further meeting with DAH about surface meteorological observations. The date of the next meeting was provisionally set for second half of June 2018. It was noted that European lidar meeting was set for the last week of June and that the NCAS/Royal Met Soc atmospheric science conference was set for 3rd and 4th July.